

Reintroducing the Direction of Evolution

Dr. Clément Vidal
Center Leo Apostel,
Vrije Universiteit Brussel
Krijgskundestraat 33, 1160 Brussels, Belgium
contact@clemvidal.com
ORCID iD: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6689-5570>
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Introduction

Teilhard was a visionary who saw a large-scale directional pattern in the unfolding of cosmic evolution. To support his vision of directed evolution, he relied on:

- 1) an internal, spiritual or “radial” energy
- 2) an epistemology hinging on final causes
- 3) a central mechanism for evolutionary change, *orthogenesis*.

Unfortunately, these three approaches have been vehemently rejected by modern science. Teilhard’s concept of “radial” energy is heavily influenced by Bergson’s (1984) now outdated *élan vital*, final causes are not considered as valid causal mechanisms, and orthogenesis -an internal directional bias- has been refuted and forgotten in favour of natural selection (reasons why Teilhard still held onto orthogenesis are exposed in Murray 1967). As Donceel (1965) wrote “It is not surprising that Teilhard insists so much on this point [of orthogenesis and directionality]. For with it his whole system stands or falls.”

Furthermore, issues of evolutionary progress and direction were excluded from the modern evolutionary synthesis by the architects of the synthesis -despite them actually believing in them (see Ruse 1996, 410–55). So we are left today with the task of explaining the directional patterns that Teilhard saw in evolution. Is it possible to reintroduce a direction of evolution without a mysterious energy, final causes or orthogenesis?

As a first step, D.S. Wilson (2022) usefully highlights developments in modern biological and cultural evolution that are compatible with Teilhard’s vision, emphasizing human cultural evolution, conscious evolution, the role of technology, up to the formation of a planetary superorganism.

However this does not do justice to the sweep of Teilhard's vision because it focuses mostly on evolutionary mechanisms that have emerged more recently during the evolution of life on Earth (e.g. artificial or social selection).

What remains to be done is to review and integrate all the directional evolutionary mechanisms that have been identified, including the ones in biological evolution. Such an integration should inform us in which ways and in how far evolution is directional or not. The challenge remains immense, but nearly all the pieces of the puzzle seem to be within our reach. Reintroducing the issue of the direction of evolution would go a long way towards probing Teilhard's vision more deeply and also to expand evolutionary theory beyond its sometimes narrow scope.

1. What directionality is not

Let us first outline what establishing a direction in evolution is *not*. First, it is wrong to reason that since evolutionary outcomes produce goal-directed organisms, evolution as a whole is goal-directed. This is an example of a *fallacy of composition*, where what is true for individual members of a class is wrongly assumed to be true for the class considered as a whole (e.g. Pirie 2006, 31).

As mentioned above, a scientific foundation for a direction in evolution can't be supported by a mysterious "radial energy", as non-natural forces are rejected by modern science; nor from a "pull" from the future -as modern science rejects finalist "explanations"; nor by the idea of a built-in direction (orthogenesis), a mechanism that has been refuted (Simpson 1949).

Turning to the related notion of *evolutionary progress*, it is inherently value laden in a way that directionality is not. Such value-ladenness often implies moral and political implications that can be highly controversial or massively misused.

Finally, one should not see directionality as a unique, deterministic direction, but a general trend, more like predicting that rain water will tend to go downhill on a mountain, not predicting every single paths of every single droplet (Vidal 2021).

2. What directionality is about

I propose to outline here some key concepts, theoretical frameworks and mechanisms that are highly promising starting points to probe and discuss the extent to which evolution is directional. The concept of *major evolutionary transitions* is especially important as it is "not restricted to human cultural evolution", as Wilson puts it. Closely related comes the concept of *evolvability* -the evolution of evolution- coupled with cooperation towards larger and larger scales (Stewart 2000; 2014; 2020). As Wilson (1997) suggests, a framework to model this rising cooperation is through *multilevel selection theory*. The science of *evolutionary-developmental biology* has also opened new understandings on the developmental constraints in evolution (e.g. Salthe 1993; Bonner 1982; Smith et al. 1985; Carroll 2005). In ecology, evolutionary trends have also been identified, for example in terms of *ecological succession* (Clements 1916) or *developmental ascendancy* (e.g. Ulanowicz 1997; Coffman 2006). Immense progress has been made

in discussing and elaborating *convergent evolution* (e.g. Conway-Morris 2003; McGhee 2011), although one should note the meaning here is *not* what Teilhard means by convergence of phyla. The field of *epigenetics* has also brought many surprises -as Wilson also points out. The issue of directionality is often discussed around the related debate of the *growth of complexity* in biological evolution (e.g. Heylighen 1999; McShea and Brandon 2010), which clearly happens for example in arms race dynamics (Dawkins et al. 1979). *Evolutionary ratchets* are also central mechanisms that seem to provide a direction (e.g. Dawkins 1997; Lukeš et al. 2011).

At the epistemological level, the concepts of *purpose*, *goal-directedness*, *teleology*, *teleonomy* or *teleodynamics* are also carefully being grounded naturalistically thanks to a wider cybernetic, systemic or complexity scientific worldview (e.g. Rosenblueth, Wiener, and Bigelow 1943; de Rosnay 1979; Deacon 2012; Corning 2014; Heylighen 2022).

Conclusion

One way to test the central issues in this debate is to ask: “What would remain the same if the tape of life were replayed?” as Gould (1990) famously asked. How would Teilhard or D.S. Wilson answer this question?

In sum, I have recalled spiritual (radial energy), scientific (orthogenesis) and epistemological (finalist reasoning) reasons why Teilhard was rejected by modern science. I argued that the first step to reintroduce Teilhard to modern evolutionary science is to reintroduce the issue of directionality in evolution. Pursuing D.S. Wilson’s efforts, our task is to continue to integrate and evaluate the extent to which new evolutionary mechanisms support or refute a general direction in biological, cultural and technological evolution.

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